

THE PERCEPTION OF THE PEOPLE OF ESAN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE, NIGERIA ON THE CAUSES OF GLOBAL WARMING

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Abstract: This paper investigates the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. Global warming refers to the long-term rise in the average temperature of the Earth's climate system, primarily driven by increased greenhouse gas emissions from human activities. Global warming is caused by natural events and human activities believed to be contributing to an increase in average global temperature. The paper investigated the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria on the major causes of global warming, the major indicators, the effects and the mitigation and adaptation strategies in the study area. To achieve these objectives, the paper used both primary and secondary sources of data collection to obtain the required data. The primary data collected from the field were through the administration of questionnaires and personal interviews. The population of the study area was projected to be 201,423 persons in 2025 at 2.5% growth rate. Out of this population, 400 respondents (0.2%) of the total population were reached via the use of structured questionnaires and oral interview. The data collected from the field were analyzed using frequency tables and percentages. From the analysis, the paper reveals that burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, bush burning, urbanization, modern agricultural practice and industrial emissions as the perception of the people on the major causes of global warming. It also shows that the major indicators of global warming in the study area are heavy and erratic rainfall, very high temperature, and deterioration of built structures. The paper also shows the perception of the people on the effects of global warming in the study area include extreme cold (the most serious effect of global warming in the study area), excessive heat, seasonal bushfires, shortage of food, serious flooding and shortage of water, and the several mitigation and adaptation strategies that have been implemented over the years to alleviate the excruciating and exacerbating effects of global warming in the study area are enhancing water conservation techniques, the use of alternative sources of power, construction of high roofs and well ventilated buildings, practicing climate-smart agriculture

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and improving cultural practice. Based on the findings, the paper, recommends the promotion of agro-forestry and sustainable farming techniques to reduce deforestation and soil degradation, encouraging the increase in the use of alternative energy sources to reduce reliance on fossil fuels for auto-mobile and generators. Community led initiatives to reduce bush burning and improve waste management, public awareness and education, measures to help modify climatic conditions in order that the temperature near the surface of the earth could be moderated to reduce global warming. The paper concludes by suggesting that government should implement policies and regulations to limit greenhouse gas emissions, promote sustainable development, encourage the people to minimize activities that drive global warming, accept and adapt to the effects of global warming with equanimity.

1 Background to the Study

Global warming can be perceived of as the recent yet ongoing rise in global average temperature near the ground or the surface of the earth. Global warming is caused by natural events and human activities believed to be contributing to an increase in average global temperature (Rimrukeh, 2009; Okhakhu, 2019). Global warming refers to the long-term rise in the average temperature of the Earth's climate system, primarily driven by increased greenhouse gas emissions from human activities (Onyekuru *et al.*, 2021; Akinyele *et al.*, 2022; IPCC, 2023). From the foregoing, global warming can be described as the recent yet ongoing rise in the average global temperature near the surface of the earth. According to Oxford Advance Learners English Dictionaries, (2025) perception refers to a belief or opinion often held by many people and based on how things seem. So, the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area (LGA), Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming can be described as the belief or opinion of the people of Esan West LGA, Edo State,

Nigeria on the causes of the recent yet ongoing rise in the average global temperature near the surface of the earth in Esan West LGA.

This phenomenon (global warming) is responsible for widespread environmental changes, including rising sea levels, altered weather patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events such as droughts and floods (IPCC, 2023). The term global warming is occasionally used to refer specifically to climate change caused by human activities as against changes in climate that may have resulted as a part of earth's natural processes (Okhakhu, 2019; Le Quéré., *et al.*, 2022; IPCC, 2023). The global scientific consensus recognizes anthropogenic emissions-particularly CO₂, methane, and nitrous oxide-as the principal drivers of these changes (Le Quéré, C., *et al.*, 2022; IPCC, 2023). Natural events and human activities are believed to be the causes of the increase in average global temperatures. This is caused mainly by increases in greenhouse gases such as Carbon Dioxide (CO₂). Greenhouse gases include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄),

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nitrous oxide (N₂O) and the halocarbons (a group of gases containing fluorine, chlorine and bromine). The accumulation of these greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, causing concentrations to increase with time is known as greenhouse effect. Global warming, characterized by the long-term rise in Earth's average surface temperature due to human activities, notably the emission of greenhouse gases, poses significant environmental and socio-economic challenges worldwide. Its effects are being increasingly felt in sub-Saharan Africa, where climate variability is disrupting traditional ways of life, particularly in rural agricultural communities. One such community is Esan West, a LGA in Edo State, Nigeria, located in the tropical rainforest zone of the southern part of the country. With an estimated average annual temperature of around 27°C and a predominantly agrarian population, the region is especially vulnerable to climate change-related impacts (NIMET, 2023). Global warming is taking place across the global community including the Humid Tropics where Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria is located. Scientific studies across the globe reveal that sea-levels are rising, snows are beginning to disappear rapidly, climate patterns are changing, the amount and pattern of precipitation are changing, more severe weather conditions including stronger tropical storms, droughts, and heat waves, Arctic shrinkage and

resulting Arctic methane release, shrinkage of the world's rainforest (already highly damaged by deforestation from logging and farming), increases in the intensity of extreme weather events, changes in agricultural yields, glacier retreat, species extinctions and changes in the ranges of disease vectors and so forth (Okhakhu, 2019; Le Quéré,., *et al.*, 2022; IPCC, 2023). Global warming has been confirmed following release of the 4th IPCC Assessment report. Africa will be worst hit by the effects of global warming and Nigeria is unarguably not an exempt (Olaniyi, Ojekunle & Amujo, 2013; Okhakhu, 2019; IPCC, 2023).

According to Okhakhu, (2019), Sulaiman & Abdul-Rahim, (2020) and Ede, (2023), Nigeria has been experiencing adverse climatic conditions with negative impacts on the welfare of millions of people. Persistent droughts and flooding, off season rains and dry spells have sent growing seasons out of orbit, on a country dependent on a rain fed agriculture. Alarm bells are ringing with lakes drying up and a reduction in river flow in the arid and semi arid regions. The result is fewer water supplies for use in agriculture, hydro power generation and other uses. The main suspect for all this havoc is global warming.

Global warming can be regarded as the biggest environmental issue of our time. It is global in its causes but its consequences are far more reaching in developing countries, like Nigeria. It

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is a topical issue across the globe because of its attendant problems that are threatening the sustenance of man and his environment. These problems are particularly becoming more severe in the under-developed and developing countries (Le Quéré, C., *et al.*, 2022; IPCC, 2023). Global warming has become the new reality of our time. It brings with it changes in weather patterns that can have serious repercussions for human beings, upsetting seasonal cycles, harming ecosystems and water supply, affecting agriculture and food production, causing sea-levels to rise. Global warming has a cumulative effect on natural resources and the balance of nature. Its effects are already visible in Nigeria (Okhakhu, 2019; Akinyele *et al.*, 2022)).

Human actions, particularly the burning of fossil fuels, are increasing atmospheric levels of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases, amplifying the greenhouse effect and increasing the temperature of the Earth's atmosphere, seas, and land surfaces. Fossil fuel combustion and massive land cover changes are both contributing to the well-documented trend of growing CO₂ levels in the atmosphere. Carbon isotopes provide the "smoking gun" that proves human activity is to blame for current increase of carbon dioxide in the air. Scientists can use these isotopes to "fingerprint" the source of carbon dioxide molecules in the atmosphere, demonstrating that greater CO₂ levels in the

atmosphere are the result of fossil fuel combustion (Weissert, 2010; World Health Organization (WHO), 2021; Akinyele *et al.*, 2022; World Bank, 2023).

2 Statement of the Problem

A crucial task for modern environmental science is to document and understand the ways in which human impacts on the earth system interact with other processes of global change. Such understanding is an essential prerequisite for establishing the consequences of further population growth and increased economic activity, with all their implications in terms of higher demands on energy, water and a wide range of resources, both renewable and non-renewable (Okhakhu, 2019).

Researches that highlight the potentially damaging effects of human activities on the environment have grown exponentially during the last decades (Okhakhu, 2019; Onyekuru *et al.*, 2021)). For instance Nwankwo & Ogundele, (2019) carried out a research on climate change education and sustainable development in Nigeria and noted that limited access to formal education and climate information, coupled with entrenched cultural beliefs, impede comprehensive understanding of anthropogenic causes of global warming. This limited perception, according to them, hinders community engagement in sustainable practices and climate mitigation. In a similar vein,

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Onyekuru *et al.*, (2021) examined the awareness and perception of climate change among rural communities in Southeast Nigeria and found that while many inhabitants notice climatic changes such as delayed rains and increased heat, a significant proportion attributed these changes to spiritual or natural causes rather than human activities. Furthermore, Ede, (2023) carried out an assessment of farmers' perception of climate change and its impact on agricultural productivity in Esan West, Edo State, Nigeria. From his findings, he reported that only about 40% of surveyed farmers recognized human-induced factors like deforestation and generator emissions as contributors to global warming while the 60% attributed the change to spiritual and natural causes. Despite these detailed and extensive studies, there is no one known to the authors that focused on the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. It is on the basis of this identified research gap that this research was carried out to fill the gap. Consequent upon the above, this paper intends to investigate the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming.

3. Aim and Objectives

The overall aim of this paper is to examine the perception of the people of Esan West Local

Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. The specific objectives are to:

- (i) examine the perception of the people of Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming;
- (ii) investigate the major indicators of global warming in Esan West, LGA, Edo State, Nigeria; and
- (iii) examine the effects of global warming on the environment of Esan West, LGA, Edo State, Nigeria
- (iv) investigate the mitigation and adaptation strategies implemented in Esan West, LGA, Edo State, Nigeria

4 Study Area

Esan West Local Government Area is one of the 18 Local Government Areas of Edo State, Nigeria. It is also one of the five Local Government Areas that constitute Esanland. The Local Government Area was created in 1991 with Ekpoma as its administrative Headquarters. The LGA is located within Latitudes $6^{\circ} 44'$ and $6^{\circ} 45'N$ of the Equator and Longitudes $6^{\circ} 06'$ and $6^{\circ} 08'E$ of the Greenwich Meridian (Ojiefu, 2005 and Esegbe, 2011; Ehisuoria & Ilenre, 2018). The LG is bounded in the north by Esan Central LGA, Owan West LGA on the North West, on the West, it is bounded by Ughunmwode l GA and to the south by Igueben LGA.

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Esan West LGA is situated on the Esan Plateau. The entire region is made up of lignite group of rocks consisting of clays, fine grained sands and carbonaceous shale clays (Omofonmwan, 2006). The relief of the area varies considerably from between 150 and 430 meters above mean sea level. The LGA has no major rivers. The major water bodies in the study area include streams such as Ibiokuima, and Ogidekpe that drain northwest of Ekpoma (Eseigbe, 2011; Ehisuoria & Ilenre, 2018). The Mobalo Stream at Urohi, which drains into Orhiomwon River, and the Olelo Stream in Ora-Ede. The other water bodies are the Amahama mysterious seasonal lake, the Egoro Springs at Emuhi, Urohi and Egoro Na-Oka axis. Water supply in the LGA is a serious challenge during the dry season particularly in Ekpoma Kingdom.

The study area is located within the tropical rain forest region. The forest consists of hard and soft woods which include Iroko, Mahogany, Africa Walnut, Black and White Afara, Obeche and Masonia (Ojiefu, 2005 and Eseigbe, 2011; Ehisuoria & Ilenre, 2018). These trees are currently more dominant at Urohi, Ogwa, Ujiogba and Iruokpen forest reserves. Human activities in the forest for agriculture (crop cultivation and animal grazing) and other economic activities have reduced the forest nature of the area. Derived savannah vegetation

plants are common in most settlements such as Emuhi, Ukhun, Ido and farm settlement.

The study area has a sub-humid tropical climate characterized by wet and dry seasons (Ojiefu, 2005; Eseigbe, 2011; Ehisuoria, 2012). The climate regime is controlled by the position of the Inter Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ). The variation between the seasons is caused by the latitudinal migration of the tropical convergence zone (ITCZ) (Eseigbe, 2009). The mean annual rainfall in Esan West is about 1,900mm to 2,000mm. The wet season lasts between March and November while the dry season is from November to March. The rainfall is highest in the months of June/July and September and lowest in the months of December to February. The annual mean temperature is between 25°C and 36°C. The current global climate change has altered the known climate of the area.

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FIG : 1.1 LOCATION: ESAN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA .
SOURCE: CartographyStudio, A.A.U.Ekpoma, 2017.

The population of the LGA in 2006 population census was estimated at 122,719 people at growth rate of 2.8% per annual. The projected

population in 2025 is 201,423 persons. The economic activities of the people include agriculture, hunting, entertainment and cottage,

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small and medium scale industrial activities. These economic activities are limited by poor transportation, flooding, low capital, bush burning, overgrazing, rural urban migration by the youths and most recently, insecurity.

5. Literature Review

Global warming is described as the recent yet ongoing rise in the average global temperature near the surface of the earth. Global warming, driven primarily by anthropogenic activities such as fossil fuel combustion, deforestation, and unsustainable agricultural practices, continues to pose serious environmental and socio-economic threats globally. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC; 2019, 2023; UNDP, 2023), global surface temperatures have reached unprecedented levels, with far-reaching consequences including rising sea levels, altered precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events. In sub-Saharan Africa-despite contributing relatively little to global emissions-the impacts of global warming are especially acute, with agriculture-dependent communities being particularly vulnerable (World Health Organization (WHO) 2021; World Bank, 2023). In Nigeria, climate-related challenges such as erratic rainfall, excessive heat, and reduced agricultural yields are becoming more prominent, especially in rural areas where livelihoods are closely tied to natural resources

(Akinyele *et al.*, 2022). Esan West, a Local Government Area (LGA) in Edo State, is one such rural setting where these effects are becoming more visible. With a tropical rainforest climate and a population heavily dependent on rain-fed agriculture, Esan West is experiencing shifting weather patterns, late rainfall onset, and unusual dry spells that negatively affect staple crops like cassava, maize, and yam.

The awareness and perception of climate change and global warming among rural populations significantly influence how communities respond to and mitigate environmental degradation. In many Nigerian rural communities, knowledge about global warming and the human role in its acceleration remain limited. Factors such as low access to environmental education, cultural beliefs, poverty, and limited governmental outreach contribute to misconceptions about the causes and effects of global warming (Onyekuru *et al.*, 2021; Ede, 2023; FAO, 2023).

Human activities such as bush burning, logging, use of diesel-powered generators, and expansion of farmlands into forested areas are common in developing countries including Esan West LGA. These activities not only contribute to environmental degradation but also reflect a disconnection between daily practices and their broader environmental consequences. This underscores the importance of understanding

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how local populations perceive their role in global warming, especially in areas heavily impacted by climate change but with limited formal education on the subject (IPCC, 2020; Onyekuru *et al.*, 2021; Ede, 2023; FAO, 2023). Recent studies emphasized that fostering climate literacy and community-based environmental awareness are essential for building climate resilience (FAO, 2022; UNDP, 2023). Without a clear understanding of the anthropogenic drivers of global warming, policy interventions and adaptation strategies may fail to gain local acceptance or bring about the necessary behavioural change.

In recent decades, climate change and global warming have emerged as critical global challenges with far-reaching consequences for both the environment and human livelihoods. Scientific evidence has firmly established that human activities-such as deforestation, fossil fuel combustion, industrial emissions, and unsustainable agricultural practices-are the primary drivers of global warming (IPCC, 2020; 2023). However, the extent to which this knowledge translates into public awareness and behavioural change varies significantly across regions, particularly in rural areas of developing countries like Nigeria.

According to IPCC, 2020 & 2023, Onyekuru *et al.*, (2021), Ede, (2023) & FAO, (2023), in the humid tropics signs of global warming are

becoming increasingly apparent. Farmers and residents have begun to observe shifts in traditional weather patterns, such as delayed rainfall, unusually high temperatures, and prolonged dry seasons. These changes have disrupted planting cycles and contributed to reduced agricultural yields, threatening food security and economic stability in the region. While these changes are acknowledged by the local population, the understanding of their root causes-especially the role of human actions-remains limited or inaccurately attributed to supernatural or natural cyclical events.

On the whole, the literature review showed that researches have been carried out in the area of global warming as well as the perception of farmers on the causes of global warming in Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria. The specific case of the perception of the people of Esan West LGA of Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming has not been examined in any study. This recent vacuum is what this current paper intends to bridge.

6 Materials and Methods

The data used in this study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data collected from the field were through the administration of questionnaires and personal interviews. The population of the study area was projected to be 201,423 persons in 2025 at 2.5% growth rate. Out this population,

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400 respondents which represent 0.2% of the total population were reached via the use of structured questionnaires and oral interview. More than half of the population of Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria is found in Ekpoma Kingdom. Owing to that, more than half of the questionnaires (250) were administered at Ekpoma kingdom. The others were administered based on the population sizes of the other communities in this order: Ogwa (45), Ukhun/Idoa (35), Ujogba (30), Urhohi (20) and Egoro (20). All the questionnaires administered were painstakingly retrieved by the researchers and their assistants and they were used to examine the objectives of the study. Personal observation was used to verify the data collected through the secondary sources with particular reference to the people's perception on the causes of global warming in the study area. The secondary data needed were collected from related and relevant published textbooks, relevant articles in journal publications, students' original essays, dissertations, theses and the internet. Others include the data generated by Esan West Local Government Council and the National Population Commission. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select the respondents in each of the Kingdoms. Questions were asked relating to the objectives of the study and other relevant areas that helped to achieve the aim of

the study. The data collected from the field were analyzed using frequency tables and percentages.

7 Results and Discussions

The perception of the people in a particular area concerning a particular subject matter is a sound reflection of several factors. These factors include but not limited to: level of education, religion, culture, superstition, level of sensitization, level of exposure, age, and amongst others.

7.1: The Perception of the People of Esan West LGA on the Causes of Global Warming

Table1 shows clearly the perception of the people of Esan West LGA of Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. Specifically, Table1 shows that 115 (28.75%) respondents perceived that burning of fossil fuels is the major cause of global warming in the study area and it is followed by deforestation which had 64 (16.00%) respondents in the study area. Bush burning recorded 48 (12.00%) respondents, urbanization recorded 42 (10.50), modern agricultural practices recorded 37 (9.25%) while industrial emissions recorded 32 (8.005%) respondents in the sty area. Other perceptions are natural forces with 23 (5.75%) respondents, increase in population with 14 (3.50%) respondents, spiritual forces 13 (3.25%) respondents, and finally neglect of traditions with 12 (3.00%) respondents in the study area. From this finding,

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it is crystal clear that the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming is in agreement with the findings of (IPCC; 2019, 2023; UNDP, 2023) that human activities-such

as deforestation, fossil fuel combustion, industrial emissions, and unsustainable agricultural practices-are the primary drivers of global warming.

Table 1The Perception of the People of Esan West LGA on the Causes of Global Warming

The people’s perception on the causes of global warming	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Industrial emissions	32	8.00
Burning of fossil fuels	115	28.75
Spiritual forces	13	3.25
Deforestation	64	16.00
Urbanisation	42	10.50
Neglect of traditions	12	3.00
Modern agricultural practices	37	9.25
Natural forces,	23	5.75
Bush burning	48	12.00
Increase in population	14	3.50
Total	400	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

7.2: The Major Indicators of Global Warming in Esan West LGA

Table 2 shows major Indicators of Global Warming in Esan West LGA (the study area). Specifically, Table 2 shows that the major indicators of global warming in the study area are heavy and erratic rainfall, very high temperature, and deterioration of built structures. This is because, heavy and erratic rainfall had 79 (19.75%) respondents, very high temperature had 70 (17.50%), and deterioration of built structures had 65 (16.50%) respondents of the sample population in the study area. In addition,

prolonged rainy season/late arrival of rainy season and disappearance of August Break both recorded 43 (10.75%) respondents, strong and stormy wind recoded 37 (9.25%) respondents, whereas, drying up of streams and rivers recorded 31 (7.75%) respondents of the sample population in the study area. Others are off season rains with 21 (5.25%) respondents, and cloudless skies with 11 (2.75%) respondents of the sample population in the study area. This finding reveals that the perception of the people of Esan West LGA on the indicators of global warming sang a concordant tune with the earlier

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findings of IPCC, (2020) & (2023), Onyekuru *et al.*, (2021), Ede, (2023) & FAO, (2023), that in the humid tropics signs/indicators of global warming are becoming increasingly apparent

and that residents have started observing shifts in traditional weather patterns, such as delayed rainfall, unusually high temperatures, and prolonged dry seasons.

Table 2 The major Indicators of Global Warming in Esan West LGA

The major indicators of global warming in Esan West LGA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Heavy and erratic rainfall	79	19.75
Very high temperature	70	17.50
Strong and stormy winds	37	9.25
Drying up of streams and rivers	31	7.75
Prolonged rainy season/late arrival of rainy season	43	10.75
Cloudless skies	11	2.75
Off season rains	21	5.25
Disappearance of August Break	43	10.75
Deterioration of built structures	65	16.50
Total	400	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

7.3 The Effects of Global Warming in Esan West LGA

Table 3 shows the responses of the people of Esan West LGA of Edo State, Nigeria on the effects of global warming in the study area. From Table 2, extreme cold which recorded 88 (22.00%) respondents is perceived as the most serious effect of global warming in the study area and it is followed by excessive heat which recorded 73 (18.25%) respondents, seasonal bushfires which recorded 58 (14.50%) respondents, shortage of food which recorded 53 (13.25%) respondents, serious flooding which recorded 48 (12.00%) and shortage of water which recorded 43 (10.75%) of the respondents in the study area. Others are emergence and

spread of diseases which recorded 21 (%) and the last on the perceived effects is migration which recorded 16 (4.00%) respondents in the study area. From this finding, it is obvious that the perception of the people of Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria on the effects of global warming in the study area is in congruence with the earlier findings of Okhakhu, (2019), Akinyele *et al.*, (2022), Ede, (2023) and FAO, (2023) that it brings with it changes in weather patterns that can have serious repercussions for human beings, upsetting seasonal cycles, harming ecosystems and water supply, affecting agriculture and food production, causing sea-levels to rise. Global warming has a cumulative effect on natural

resources and the balance of nature. Its effects are already visible in Nigeria.

Table 3 The effects of global warming in Esan West LGA

The effects of global warming in Esan West LGA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Serious flooding	48	12.00
Migration	16	4.00
Excessive heat	73	18.25
Extreme cold	88	22.00
Shortage of food	53	13.25
Emergence and spread of diseases	21	5.25
Seasonal bushfires	58	14.50
Shortage of water	43	10.75
Total	400	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

7.4 The Mitigation, and Adaptation Strategies in Esan West LGA

Given the obvious threat posed by global warming to man, his environment and sustenance in Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria, several mitigation and adaptation strategies have been put in place and implemented over the years to alleviate the excruciating and exacerbating effects of global warming in the study area which include but not limited to; enhancing water conservation techniques, such as improving rainwater harvesting techniques, artificial recharge techniques, and digging/sinking of boreholes/wells; the use of alternative sources of power, construction of high roofs and well ventilated buildings; practicing climate-smart agriculture which includes incorporating climate-hazard resistant crops; and improving

cultural practices, such as proper drainage and canopy management that are able to mitigate risks associated with rainfall and temperature extremes.

8 Conclusion

This paper investigated the perception of the people of Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. The findings revealed that human activities such as burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, industrial processes, agricultural practices, use of fluorinated gases and so forth contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions, leading to global warming. The study also showed that the effects of global warming are evident in Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria with rising temperatures, changing rainfall patterns, dropping relative humidity and increased frequency of extreme weather events. This paper has demonstrated

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that human activities play a significant role in contributing to global warming in Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria. The findings highlight the need for urgent action to mitigate the effects of global warming and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria

9. Recommendations

This paper investigated the perception of the people of Esan West LGA, Edo State, Nigeria on the causes of global warming. Based on the findings of this paper, the following actionable policy recommendations are made: promotion of agro-forestry and sustainable farming techniques to reduce deforestation and soil degradation, encouraging the increase in the use of alternative energy sources to reduce reliance on fossil fuels for auto-mobile and generators, community led initiatives to reduce bush burning and improve waste management, public awareness and education, measures to help modify climatic conditions in order that the temperature near the surface of the earth can be moderated to reduce global warming, public awareness campaigns and educational programs should be implemented to educate residents about the causes and effects of global warming and the importance of sustainable practices, the government should implement policies and regulations to limit greenhouse gas emissions, promote sustainable development, encourage the people to minimize activities that drive global

warming, accept and adapt to the effects of global warming with equanimity.

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